

Emotion-Aware Empathetic Response System via BERT-driven Lion Architecture for Campus-based Mental Health Support

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Abstract

Presently, mental health challenges among adolescents aged 18 to 22 have emerged as a critical concern necessitating urgent intervention. Statistics indicate that over 75% of individuals with mental health conditions in Thailand face significant barriers to care due to a severe shortage of professionals and high service costs [1]. This treatment gap is compounded by the increasing prevalence of depressive symptoms among university-aged youth, requiring scalable digital solutions [2], [3]. In response, the Flourich project introduces Safe Room, an intelligent chatbot platform designed as a primary psychological support system. Developed in collaboration with clinical psychologists from Rangsit University, the Safe Room interaction logic is grounded in professional clinical expertise and evidence-based psychological intervention principles [4], [5].

Technically, the platform implements a sequential hybrid pipeline. Following a successful pilot phase using Google Gemini to establish conversational benchmarks, the system has been advanced through a specialized BERT-driven Lion Architecture. In contrast to earlier models developed for general purposes, this study specifically addresses the linguistic nuances of the Thai language by integrating a localized emotion-aware framework. As illustrated in Figure 1: System Workflow of the Emotion-Aware Consultation Model, the core methodology follows the framework proposed in [6], which ensures the seamless fusion of semantic content and affective states by integrating an emotion detector module with a generative backbone.

The system utilizes WangchanBERTa as an emotion classifier, fine-tuned on the Wiselight Sentiment Corpus [7]. Performance evaluations demonstrate the classifier's high precision, achieving an F1-score of 0.92 for the negative class and 0.88 for the positive class. These results significantly outperform standard non-localized classifiers in identifying Thai emotional valences. These identified emotional categories are subsequently transformed into emotion embeddings and integrated as contextual labels for the WangChan Lion IT V3 (LLM). The LLM component underwent instruction tuning using specialized empathetic datasets, including MentalChat16K [8] and ESConv [9].

This architecture enables Emotion-Aware Responses that dynamically adapt to the user’s emotional valence [10]. To demonstrate the effectiveness of emotion conditioning, preliminary comparative analyses indicate that the integrated emotion-aware pipeline provides higher empathy scores and more relevant supportive dialogues than standard generative baselines without emotion labels. All computational workloads are optimized to ensure high-performance, real-time inference. Preliminary evaluations, incorporating both automated metrics and empathy assessments [11], demonstrate that the architecture delivers highly empathetic dialogues capable of stabilizing emotional distress. To improve the system’s efficacy, our future work will focus on evaluating the model’s longitudinal impact on user well-being and expanding the implementation to a university-wide scale. Furthermore, we aim to integrate more diverse clinical datasets to enhance the system’s utility as a triage tool for psychiatrists and medical personnel at the provincial level.

Figure 1: System Workflow of the Emotion-Aware Consultation Model.

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